

Chief Executive Officer with Machiavellianism Trait and Survival of Family-owned Businesses in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract:

Family-owned businesses (FOBs) are seen as a major contributor to economic growth and development in the global economy. It has nothing to do with the important role they continue to play in job creation, the growth of business enterprises in communities, and the growth of gross domestic product (GDP). Sadly, in addition to their national development efforts, only a small percentage of these family-owned businesses survive the second and third generations. This astonishing practice worries many scholars who claim that these failures are embedded in poor asset systems, incompetence of the management team, poor transformation plans, etc. CEOs and the survival of these family-owned businesses was limited. This multidisciplinary study examined the personality traits of CEOs in Machiavellianism in the southern region of Nigeria and the survival of family-owned businesses. This study is tied to the Sustainable Family Business Theory (SFBT). The study consisted of 628 people, with 289 participants from hotels in the southern region of Nigeria. A structural model used for data analysis, CEO Machiavellianism points out that personality traits are negatively related to the survival of family-owned businesses.

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1.0 Introduction

Family-owned businesses (FOBs) have been commended as promoters of economic growth and development in a developing and emerging economy. This is due to their role in job creation, the growth of young entrepreneurs, national product production, etc. (Lee, Vargo, & Seville, 2013; Perett, Burnett, & Richardson, 2017). In Spain, about 1500 of the top 3000 companies belong to families, while in the US and Canada, 90 percent of businesses in these countries are FOB and account for 50 percent of US GDP. Half of the American workforce is employed by family-owned businesses (Astrachan & Colenco, 1994) and 35% of top American companies are family-owned (Moore, 2008). Ibrahim and Ellis (1994) found that family-owned businesses account for 48 percent of the workforce and generate approximately 50 percent of Canada's GDP. Family-owned businesses make up about one-third of the list of major companies Fortune 500 (Ibrahim, Soufani, and Lam, 2003). According to Utami, Bernardus and Shinta (2015), family-owned enterprises make up 62% of US workers and account for 64% of gross domestic product (GDP) nationwide. In China, 70% of large corporations belong to the family, while in India 20 large corporate entities and 66% of the private sector assets are controlled by family-owned companies (Utami et al., 2015). According to Bednorz, Belyusky, Nikodenska-Vonovic, and Otukoya (2017), in 2015, there were 7.4 million private companies in the People's Republic of China (PRC) and 85.4% of family-owned businesses. FOBs recruit at least 7 employees increased from 24.64 million in 2005 to 34 million in 2015. As of 2015, one-third of the companies listed in China are family owned (Kai, 2015).

Although FOBs have contributed significantly to the global economy, only a few survive the second and third generations (Asaju, Arom, & Mukaila, 2014; Bednorz et al., 2017; Kai, 2015; Gaumer & Shaffer, 2018; Ravindra Hewa Kurupuge & Gregor, 2017; Ravindra Hewa Kurupuge & Gregor, 2018; Mokhber et al., 2017; Peret et al., 2017; Stafford, Bhargava, Danes, Haynes, & Bruton, 2010). This is a compulsory professional case. Focusing their attention on the long-term existence of FOBs. Investigators say family-owned businesses are responsible for growth, but sadly, about 85 percent of FOBs fail. Of these few survivors, only 30% (i.e., one-third) are successfully transferred to the next generation of family founders (Poza, 2013) and only 10-15% are passed on to the third generation (Birley, 1986; Bretton- Miller, Miller, & Steer, 2004). According to Miller, Steer and Le Bretton-Miller (2003) these failures are due to estate inequalities. Ibrahim, Dumas, and McGuire (2001) argue that the conflict between family traditions and business principles is due to poor quality of life, which has created serious problems. They point to some of these issues including conflict, inheritance issues, and other administrative-related issues. Lansberg (1999) identified the lack of a sequence system as a major cause of FOB failure. Only 30% and 14% of family-owned businesses survive the second and third generation. Onuoha (2012) believes that the average life expectancy of FOBs in Nigeria or around the world is 24 years. Paret et al. (2017) found that improving the succession process can reduce the failure of a family-owned business. Some scholars in the family business have recognized that a leadership style is the decisive factor in the survival and success of these businesses because ethical and ethical factors influence the business outcomes (Asaju et al., 2014; Morey, 2008). CEOs are more concerned with business continuity and ownership transformation, so the personality traits of a CEO that have brought success and business survival are ignored (Astrachan & Kolenko, 1994; Astrachan & Shankar, 2003; Poza, 2013). To ensure business continuity, the leader or successor must have the necessary leadership skills and / or personality traits that will move the business to the next generation (Ibrahim et al., 2003; Poza, 2013).

The gaps based on the literature review indicate that there have been many studies on the survival of family-owned businesses, but the main focus is on organizing the sequence and that Chief Executive Officer (CEO) Machiavellianism is not a human tradition. Few studies have used standardized modeling (SEM) and AMOS software to determine the effect of CEO Machiavellianism personality on the survival of family-owned businesses. This creates the impetus for this study, which seeks to look at the impact of CEO Machiavellianism on the survival of family-owned businesses. Research is trying to fill some gaps in the literature. First, the study carefully examined the personalities and businesses owned by the family of CEO Machiavellianism in southern Nigeria. In addition, this study provided the benefit of a non-brainwashing investigation into the personality of CEO Machiavellianism and the survival of family-owned businesses using Structural Equation Model (SEM).

This study attempts to answer the following research questions:

What is the relationship between Machiavellianism and compatibility?

What is the relationship between Machiavellianism and dynamic efficiency?

What is the relationship between Machiavellianism and competitiveness?

The following null research hypotheses were developed and tested in the study:

H01: There is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and compatibility.

H02: There is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and dynamic efficiency.

H03: There is no significant link between Machiavellianism and competitiveness.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The study hosted the Sustainable Family Business Theory (SFBT) which provided the research anchor. The Sustainable Family Business Theory (SFBT) was presented by Stafford, Duncan, Dane, and Winter (1999), and later Danes, Lee, Stafford, & Heck (2008). Proper theoretical ideas are: (a) capital transactions in firm or family spheres may facilitate or inhibit firm sustainability (Haynes, Danes, & Stafford, 2011), (b) owning family members interact by exchanging capital across firm and family boundaries (Danes, Stafford, & Loy, 2007), (c) the family or business system can die if the boundaries are too wide (Stafford et al., 1999), and (d) good social, family and community relationship enhances community productivity (Nehm, Swinney, & Miller, 2008).

This vision aims to address the challenges associated with the long-term sustainability of the family business by recognizing the trust and reliance on family, business and public enterprise management. This view examines the economic, social and social impact of the family system on long-term business sustainability (Danes et al., 2008; Gibb Dyer Jr., 2006). The capital letter in this context refers to finances, personal qualities, skills, knowledge, strength, communication, or experience that help to achieve certain goals. A family who owns a business can invest capital directly or indirectly depending on their skills and financial planning. In SFBT, family capital is defined as the complete resources (personal, social and economic) held by family members who are business owners (Stafford et al., 2010). It is usually a fundraiser for all family members (Oughton & Willock, 2003). Large family finances determine their positive potential in a turbulent business environment (Dananan et al., 2008). According to Danes, Stafford, Haynes and Amarpurkar (2009), family finances affect the performance and stability of a business depending on the sector; and the impact of financial stability on business stability in the industry varies greatly (Danes et al., 2007). Bird and Brush (2002) consider gender equality when looking at the strength and resilience of an organization (Quake-Bunn, 2013). SFBT sees social benefits as an interest within your family members and between their families and their host communities. It describes the relationships that exist between people. Public funds provide information, technology,

market access and related resources (Hit, Ireland, Camp, and Sexton, 2002). Depending on the structure and constraints of the business, SFBT transforms inputs into short-term and long-term success and sustainability, respectively. In the short term, processes use money to create or increase other revenue (Danes, Router, Kwan, & Doherty, 2002).

2.2 The Concept of CEO Personality Trait

Senior executives often face decision-making challenges such as “overload of information, confusing indicators and conflicting intentions and intentions” so that their decisions and actions further their personality (Carpenter et al., 2004, p. 750). As a result of the CEO's negative rating tool, personality traits are not understood (Hiller & Humbrick, 2005). The personality studies of the CEO have been found to influence the strategic, structural and operational decisions of his organization (Hambrick, 2007; Shane, 2010). This explains why Hambrick, Finkelstein and Mooney (2005, p. 503) emphasized the importation of higher education. However, although many scholars represent personality traits with the “Big Five” (5) (a) conscientiousness (b) agreeableness (c) neuroticism (d) Openness to experience and (e) extraversion, this study seeks to address other trait which is Machiavellianism.

2.3 Machiavellianism Personality Trait

"Machiavellianism" is taken from Renaissance writer Niccol Machiavelli, who provided detailed information on the emperor's tactics in obtaining and retaining power in his work, the Prince. Niccol Machiavelli describes Machiavelli as a person who uses others to achieve his goals. They deceive and deceive others for the sake of their own good (Berezky, Birkas, and Kerex, 2010). American scholars Richard Christie and Florence Geese first studied Machiavellianism from a psychological point of view, describing it as an aspect of humanity, attitude, and morality in the world. They saw that Machiavellianism, in the beginning, was not the object of the leaders; Second, it is not a dictatorial personality; Third, it is more than just a mental illness. They were of the opinion that the general public could reflect the Machiavellian view. Everyone, except his social class, has a tendency to deceive others. In a book published in 1970, Richard Christie and Florence Geese have five major Machiavellian characteristics: manipulation, amorality, cynicism, emotional coldness and a lack of empathy (Berezky et al., 2010).

Manipulation

Machiavellians Control: They use, deceive and change others. They were always misleading others (Sutton & Kiyog, 2000). They are harsh, selfish, and cruel in their relationships. Machiavellian leaders have had a detrimental effect on the success of the work and the well-being of their employees (Wolmer, Coach, & Goritz, 2016). Machiavellians only choose to fish in troubled waters where they are unlikely to be exposed. They are more likely to justify their actions for a reason, saying that others will do the same if given the opportunity. They research a number of ways to deceive others: they may be flattering, abusive, or cooperative. The Machiavellians are not hostile and aggressive, but they have many strategies in their relationships (Jones & Paulus, 2009, p. 93). One secret to the success of the Machiavellians lies in the many different tactics they use to deceive others. Deception has many facets for lying. Machiavellians often lie and lie with confidence and success.

Amorality

Machiavellians are prone to amorality; They can easily separate themselves from moral understanding. They are always pursuing their own interests, and they are not so restricted by moral restrictions. They are determined to break the rules of conduct if they expect to gain material gain (Woodley & Allen, 2014). In general, they are not interested in principles such

as impartiality, retaliation and commitment. They do not believe in such texts because some are equally disrespectful and violate moral principles, but they claim to be arguing hypocritically. According to Christie and Geese (2013) one of the most important characteristics of Machiavellians is their ability to withstand public expectations, not to let social norms and values influence them, and therefore their tendency to deceive.

Cynicism

Machiavellians have deep cynicism. They do not care about others and do not think well of other people (Pilch, 2008). They always say bad things to people because they see others as hypocrites, liars and crooks. The obvious feature of Machiavellian is insecurity. Machiavellians often criticize others because they view others as dishonest (Christie & Geese, 2013). They believe that others will not think the same thing about them, and they will mislead them if given the opportunity. McElwain (2003) suggests that Machiavellians use their hatred to create an imbalance of power between themselves and their potential victims. They are seen as small discussion groups. They feel that some people are worse off than they really are because of the knowledge they have gained and the confidence they have in others. They believe that people without internal power are driven by external forces.

Emotional coldness

Machiavellians have a reserved, irrational, and indifferent attitude. They often put emotions aside when they are faced with situations; and they don't care about the feelings of others. They try to maintain a positive attitude by considering things and people. Focus on the goals and not the people. Machiavellians focus on their own interests and ignore the interests of others (Christie & Geese, 2013; Howley, 2006). Machiavellians think logically and explore opportunities in a logical way (Pilch, 2008). They are always in control of their emotions and their emotions do not determine their actions.

Lack of empathy

The factors mentioned above are related to lack of empathy shown by Machiavellians. They cannot empathize with others emotionally. Machiavellians show the worst skills to experience the joys, sorrows or disappointments of others, so it is difficult for them to help those in need. They may ignore the pain or the intent that their victims are causing. They are happy to mislead others, to violate moral standards, and to suffer the hurt of others. They rarely suffer the pain of others; their focus is on their books and intentions and not on anyone else. They are free to distrust and deceive others. Machiavellian empathy can be viewed in two ways (powerful and sensible empathy), but scholars say that Machiavellians are wrong only in their active empathy (emotional sharing) and not in showing empathy (awareness and understanding) (Routhman & Will, 2011; Weselka et al., 2010; Woodley & Allen, 2014).

Machiavellians also find it difficult to express their feelings and do not find happiness (Nolan, Desmond, Herlich, & Hardy, 1986; Robot, 1896; Sifnios, 1973). In addition, people with alexithymia have (1) difficulty in recognizing their emotions, (2) difficulty distinguishing between their mood and physical condition, (3) limited inaction and creative skills, (4) lack of self-assessment skills (Berezki et al, 2010; Howley, 2006; Hodgson, Hogg, & McInnes, 2009; Kerrig & Stelwagen, 2010; Richardson, & Thepot, 2007). One secret to the success of Machiavellians lies in the many different tactics they use to deceive others. Manipulation is multifaceted with lying. Machiavellians often lie and they lie confidently and effectively.

Amorality

Machiavellians tend to behave immorally; They can easily distinguish themselves from moral understanding. They always pursue their advantage, and they are not particularly deterred by moral prohibitions. They are willing to break the rules of morality when they expect material gain (Woodley & Allen, 2014). In general, they are not interested in terms such as fairness, reciprocity and responsibility. They do not believe in such terms because others equally disrespect and violate moral principles, yet they claim to be hypocritically opposed. According to Christie and Geese (2013) one of the most important characteristics of Machiavellians is their ability to resist social expectations, not to let social norms and principles influence them, and therefore their manipulative tendencies.

Cynicism

Machiavellians have deep cynicism. They care less about others and do not think positively about other people (Pilch, 2008). They constantly attribute negative traits to people because they see others as hypocrites, liars and villains. One obvious feature of Machiavellian is distrust. Machiavellians are constantly suspicious of others because they consider others to be dishonest (Christie & Geese, 2013). They believe that others will not think the same of them, and will mislead them if given the opportunity. McElwain (2003) suggests that Machiavellians use their aversion to create an energy imbalance between themselves and their potential victims. They are seen as less parties to negotiate with others. They feel that others are worse than they are because of the knowledge they have perceived and their trust in other people. They believe that people other than internal forces are driven by external forces.

Cold Mindedness

Machiavellians have a reserved, cold-blooded and indifferent attitude. They usually put emotions aside when dealing with situations; And they do not care about the feelings of others. They try to maintain a rational attitude when considering things and people. They are goal-oriented and not person-oriented. Machiavellians focus on their own interests and ignore the interests of others (Christie & Geese, 2013; Howley, 2006). Machiavellians think rationally and examine opportunities in a cold-minded manner (Pilch, 2008). They always control their emotions and their emotions do not determine their actions.

Lack of empathy

The features discussed above are related to the lack of recognizable empathy with Machiavellians. They cannot get emotional sympathy with others. Machiavellians show very poor abilities to accustom themselves to the joys, pains or disappointments of others, and therefore, it is difficult for them to help those in trouble. They may ignore the pain they cause or the intent to cause it to their victims. They take pleasure in misleading others, violating moral standards, and being hurt by the emotions of others. They rarely suffer with others 'pain; Their focus is on their own views and intentions and not on anyone else. They are comfortable distrusting and deceiving others. The expression of Machiavellian empathy can be viewed from two perspectives (influential and cognitive empathy), but scholars say that Machiavellians only have a flaw in their effective empathy (sharing of emotions) and not in the display of cognitive empathy (recognizing and understanding) "Reading the Mind in the Eyes Other people's emotions are intact using the "Tom Test" (McElwain, 2003; Routhman & Will, 2011; Weselka, Schermer, Martin, & Vernon, 2010; Woodley & Allen, 2014). Machiavellians also find it difficult to identify their own emotions and they do not experience pleasure (Nolan, Desmond, Herlich, & Hardy, 1986; Robot, 1896; Sifnios, 1973). In addition, people with alexithymia have (1) difficulties in recognizing their emotions / feelings, (2)

difficulties in distinguishing their mental state from their physical or physical condition, (3) limited ination and creative abilities, (4) lack of introspection abilities (Berezki et al, 2010; Howley, 2006; Hodgson, Hogg, & McInnes, 2009; Kerrig & Stelwagen, 2010; Richardson, & Thepot, 2007).

2.4 The Concept of Organizational Survival

The business climate is characterized by uncertainty and unpredictable events that threaten the survival of the organization. If these issues are not handled properly companies lose out on sales and profits. The continued persistence of these bad practices disrupts / affects the company's need to continue operating to meet the expectations of shareholders; a situation where good reputation, reputation and corporate customers are often lost. The improper management of these ants can challenge the organization's survival and survival, leading to its eventual collapse (Fleming, 2012).

2.5 Adaptability

In the current volatile and uncertain business environment, organizational survival depends on the organisation's ability to adapt to climate change and to adjust its processes. Residents change the delivery of their products, but often need to change and / or adjust their strategies. In doing so, an organization should regularly scan its environment, identify critical changes, and quickly refine or rebuild its business model to address changes (Reeves & Daimler, 2012). Reeves and Deamler (2012) suggested that companies need to adapt more quickly by making annual planning processes more repetitive and continuous. By exploring the environment today companies can detect, assess and analyze signs of uncertainty and make changes that will have a positive impact on their survival. According to Dennison (1990), three areas of coherence have been identified that affect well-functioning organizations. First, organizations recognize and respond to the environment. Second, they respond to internal customers. Third, they change or correct their behaviour. These positive responses ensure the survival of the organization. Denison (1990) suggested dynamic factors including transformation creation, customer focus and organizational learning. Lee (1999) and Link and Link (1995) support the view that organizational learning organizations are an integral part of climate change adaptation.

2.6 Dynamic Capability

Dynamic capability is when a company chief executive transforms or rebuild existing skills and resources to meet business needs (Zahra, Sapphire, & Davidson, 2006). The vision of Organizational Dynamic Capability (DC) defines it as a continuous structure of organizational mechanisms for maintaining business growth. It involves inventing new things and adapting to changing markets. Responsive and fast-moving organizations in new product development, capacity building and capacity building improve performance; Such companies can easily regain the ability to meet changing market demands (Wang, 2013). Dynamic strengths are determined by learning methods such as repetition, trial and error, experience and market flexibility. Dynamic capability differs in operating capacity relative to the current performance of organizations; It is concerned with deliberately building, enlarging or altering its resource base (Chang, How, & Lin, 2013).

2.7 Competitiveness

Competition enhances organizational impact, growth management and performance and improves organizational performance. This makes it more profitable and increases the market share compared to other competitors. A competing company uses all of its resources (equipment and human resources), provides adequate benefits to all stakeholders and

successfully achieves its goal by providing state-of-the-art products / services cheaper than its competitors. This is possible because developed and offered products / services are different and may exceed market quality standards. Kisiel-cowczyc (2009) found that developing a competitive strategy is essential to the survival and development of any organization or organizations.

Matiza (2016) divides competition into three types:

General Competition - where the actual results match the expectations of the participating participants;

Under normal competition - where the actual results fall short of expectations. Shareholders may leave the company and move on to another attractive company;

In addition to the usual competition - when the actual results exceed expectations. Shareholders strengthened their relationship with the company.

Competition is related to factors and may be related to outcome. Reality-related competition means the potential use of organizational assets and personnel to create market competition. Outcome-related competition that creates competition in the company's market share, product sales volume and financial performance compared to the average-industry (Lubiasky, Michelsky, & Misala, 1995).

Competition can be both performance and system-related. Work-related competition means creating competition for the technical skills of employees. System-related competition in which an organization is governed by four different levels: mega, macro, miso, and micro (Mroziowski, 2011).

3.0 Research Method

The population of this study are a complete list of hotels registered in the southern regions of Nigeria, which contains a sample frame. Sample units (these are informal sector hotels) were taken from the list of members of the Hotel Proprietors Association in six (6) states in southern Nigeria (Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross Rivers, Delta, Edo and Rivers State). The population of the study population was 628 and the participants from the population were 289. The study used a deliberate random approach and used a simple random sample with the help of random numbers, each member having an equal chance of being randomly selected.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Hypothesis One

H0₁: No significant relationship between Machiavellianism and adaptability.

Table 1 below shows an analysis between the correlation of Machiavellianism and adaptability of FOBs in southern Nigeria, where $\beta = -0.20$, $r = -0.19$, $R^2 = 0.04$ and $p = 0.000$. The study showed a negative and significant correlation between these two variables (when $\beta = -0.20 < 0.3$, $r = -0.19 < 0.7$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, based on the acceptance process ($\beta > 0.3$, $r > 0.7$ and $p > 0.05$); or rejection ($\beta < 0.3$, $r < 0.7$ and $p < 0.05$), rejection of the null hypothesis also restates that there is a negative relationship between Machiavellianism and adaptability of FOBs in southern Nigeria. Therefore, H0₁ is not supported.

Hypothesis Two

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and dynamic capability

Table 2 below shows the relationship between Machiavellianism and the dynamic capability of FOBs in southern Nigeria, where $\beta = -0.26$, $r = -0.20$, $R^2 = 0.07$ and $p = 0.000$. Investigations show a negative and significant correlation between the two variables (when $\beta = -0.26 < 0.3$, $r = -0.20 < 0.7$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, depending on the acceptance criteria for the null hypothetical statement acceptance ($\beta > 0.3$, $r > 0.7$ and $p > 0.05$); or rejection ($\beta < 0.3$, $r < 0.7$ and

$p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis was rejected and emphasized that there was a negative relationship between Machiavellianism and the dynamic capability of FOBs in southern Nigeria. Therefore, H02 is not supported.

Hypothesis Three

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and competitiveness.

Table 3 below shows the relationship between Machiavellianism and the competitiveness of FOBs in South-South Nigeria, where $\beta = -0.26$, $r = -0.20$, $R^2 = 0.07$ and $p = 0.000$. Investigations show a negative and significant correlation between the two variables (where $\beta = -0.26 < 0.3$, $r = -0.20 < 0.7$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Therefore, depending on the acceptance criteria for the null hypothetical statement acceptance ($\beta > 0.3$, $r > 0.7$ and $p > 0.05$); or rejection ($\beta < 0.3$, $r < 0.7$ and $p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected and restate the fact that there is a negative relationship between Machiavellianism and competitiveness of FOBs in south-south Nigeria. Therefore, H03 is not supported. Presented in Table 4 below is the result of hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 of the study, which assesses the extent to which Machiavellianism affects the measures of FOB survival. The first hypothesis (H01) states that there is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and adaptability. However, Table 4 shows that Machiavellianism has a negative and significant correlation with adaptability of hotels in the south-south region of Nigeria ($\beta = -0.20$, $r = -0.19$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.005$). Therefore, H01 is not supported. Machiavellianism is presented as a weak and negative predictor of adaptability of hotels in South-south Nigeria. Statistically, it shows that when Machiavellianism goes up by 1 standard deviation, adaptability goes down by -0.20 standard deviation. In other words, when Machiavellianism goes up by 1, adaptability goes down by -0.19. The weight of the relevance of Machiavellianism in the coherence scale varies from zero to 0.005 on the scale (two tails). Evidence shows that the personality traits of a CEO, such as cheating, misleading, and altering a hotel's ability to adapt to changes in business, are negatively affected because hotel performance is not good for certain things, but actually learning how to do new things that show adaptability. It should be good. This suggests that the rise of Machiavellianism is associated with a decline in adaptability. This position has been confirmed by Christie and Geese (2013), who recognize that the characteristics of Machiavellianism have a negative impact on the business outcomes of many organizations. The senior management of this aspect is of the opinion that they are living up to the expectations of the community and not allowing social norms and values to influence them. The second theory (H02) states that there is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and dynamic capability. However, Table 4 suggests that Machiavellianism has a negative and significant relationship with the dynamic capability of hotels in the south-south region of Nigeria ($\beta = -0.26$, $r = -0.20$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.005$). Therefore, H02 is not supported. This means that the presence of Machiavellianism in hotels in southern Nigeria does not lead to strong performance. Statistically, this shows that while Machiavellianism 1 increased by a standard deviation, the strongest efficiency decreased with a standard deviation of 0.26. In other words, as Machiavellianism goes up by 1, dynamic capability goes down by -0.20. The weight of the relapse of Machiavellianism in the degree of dynamic capability is very different from zero at the level of 0.005 (two tails). This suggests that the rise of Machiavellianism is associated with a decrease in dynamic capability.

This position was confirmed by Wolmer et al. (2016) Machiavellianism suggests that leaders with personality traits prefer to fish in troubled waters only when they see that they are less likely to be exposed and that they have reasons in their actions for a specific reason, namely organizational performance and survival. Therefore, it can be said that the CEO's personality is willing to violate ethical and unpopular norms in terms of flexibility, regression and

commitment, which are not essential ways to transform or establish important skills according to hotel objectives. Evidence suggests that such behaviour, which reflects Machiavellianism, strongly attracts hotels' desire to learn more about the integration of production methods in terms of unfinished goods and the integration of technology. The third view (H03) states that there is no significant relationship between Machiavellianism and competitiveness. However, Table 4 suggests that Machiavellianism has a negative and significant relationship with hotel competitiveness in south-south Nigeria ($\beta = -0.14$, $r = -0.13$ and $p = 0.000 < 0.005$). Therefore, H03 is not supported. That is to say, Machiavellianism does not overstate the competitiveness of hotels in south-south Nigeria. Statistically, it shows that when Machiavellianism goes up by 1 standard deviation, adoption of competitive strategies goes down by -0.14 standard deviation. In other words, as Machiavellianism trait increases, acceptance of competitive strategies decreases by -0.13. This suggests that the rise of Machiavellianism was accompanied by competitiveness. This finding agrees with Pilch (2008) that CEOs with this personality traits do not believe in what others say or do. They do not think in the right way. It affects their desire to embrace new and / or competitive strategies; Also employ employees with the necessary skills and competencies. They believe that they can do everything they can. The weight of the relapse of Machiavellianism in measuring competitiveness varies from zero to 0.005 on the scale (two tails).

These results show that Machiavellianism has negative consequences and significantly affects the survival of family-owned hotels in south-south Nigeria; and exhibition of Machiavellianism trait by hotel CEOs will lead to inability to use competitive strategies, attract family and employees with the necessary knowledge, creative skills, and maintain good relations between shareholders. In some lands, Machiavellianism does not have the power to attract workers with personality traits that reflect the knowledge, skills, and abilities to perform any task at a given time and with available resources. Based on these results, the study found the following:

Machiavellianism does not give hotels the ability to adjust their processes and policies in response to climate change in south- south Nigeria. Machiavellianism does not increase the capacity of hotels to continue building and improving institutional learning that will maintain business growth and survival in South-south Nigeria. Machiavellianism does not contribute to the hotels ability to attract family and staff members with requisite experience, creative and innovative capabilities to assume management position and drive growth aspirations in South-south Nigeria. Thus, all three null hypothetical statements of no significant relationships between Machiavellianism and the measures of survival of FOBs are rejected based on the lack of statistical evidence to show otherwise.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The study confirms, based on its observations and strong evidence, that the CEO Machiavellianism personality trait play a vital and important role in initiating the coherence, efficiency and competitiveness of hotels in south-south Nigeria. The results continue to prove and lend to the fact that the personalities of CEOs are the most important factor in maintaining business performance and survival; Its role as a precursor to the survival of family-owned businesses is important, as CEOs need knowledge and personality in their decisions and strategic decisions that have a positive impact on organizational performance and survival. In general, most of the findings and conclusions of this study have implications because they support or reject previous studies from the literature. Specifically, this study has an impact on the CEO's personality records and the survival of family-owned businesses. Also, the results of research have had an impact on businesses that do not care about the personality that their managers require in order to survive.

It also addresses the issues and ideas of a sustainable family business that family finance (human, economic and social) will contribute to the long-term performance and sustainability of firms; and managers who point to their organizations and are more committed to organizational values (Danes et al., 2008; Gibb Dyer Jr., 2006). They provide an end to organization because of internal motivation, deep emotional involvement, personal happiness, and reputation. Based on the findings and conclusions of this study regarding the relationship between CEO Machiavellianism personality and survival of family-owned businesses in south-south Nigeria, the study recommends that CEOs as executives must control and / or manage their Machiavellianism personality, which makes their relationships treacherous, deceptive, extremely strong, selfish and cruel, morally, distrustful, ruthless, and so on. Solving, anticipating and anticipating problems and developing problems are timely solutions and continuous construction and building organizational mechanisms that will sustain business growth and survival.

Figure 1: Relationship between Machiavellianism and adaptability of FOBs in South-South Nigeria

Table 1: Relationship between Machiavellianism and adaptability of FOBs in South-South Nigeria

Mediation Stage	Relationship	Chi Square(df), Significance	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
MAC → ADAP (Hypothesis 1)	Machiavellianism and adaptability	(19df) = 81.589, P<0.000	0.98	0.96	0.98	0.11
Regression Weights	Std. Beta (β)	Squared Multiple correlation (R²)	CMIN/DF			
-0.188	-0.203	0.041	4.294			

Source: Amos 26.0 output on research data, 2020

Figure 2: Relationship between Machiavellianism and dynamic capability of FOBs in South-South Nigeria

Table 2: Relationship between Machiavellianism and dynamic capability of FOBs in South-South Nigeria

Mediation Stage	Relationship	Chi Square(df), Significance	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
MAC → DYN (Hypothesis 2)	Machiavellianism and Dynamic Capability	(19df) = 93.880, P<0.000	0.97	0.94	0.98	0.12
Regression Weights	Std. Beta (β)	Squared Multiple correlation (R²)	CMIN/DF			
-0.199	-0.257	0.066	4.941			

Source: Amos 26.0 output on research data, 2020

Figure 3: Relationship between Machiavellianism and Competitiveness of FOBs in South-South Nigeria

Table 3: Relationship between Machiavellianism and competitiveness of FOBs in South-South Nigeria

Mediation Stage	Relationship	Chi Square(df), Significance	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
MAC → COMP (Hypothesis 3)	Machiavellianism and Competitiveness	(22df) = 98.225, P<0.000	0.97	0.94	0.98	0.12
Regression Weights	Std. Beta (β)	Squared Multiple correlation (R ²)	CMIN/DF			
-0.199	-0.257	0.066	4.465			

Source: Amos 26.0 output on research data, 2020

Table 4: Summary of Result on the Tests of Hypotheses H0₁; H0₂ and H0₃

S/N	Mediation Stage (Null Hypothesis)	Relationship	Std. Beta	Actual Beta	R ²	CMIN/DF	P	Remark	Decision
1	X → Y (H0 ₁)	Machiavellianism and Adaptability	- 0.20	-0.19	0.04	4.29	0.000	Negative and Significant	Not supported
2	X → Y (H0 ₂)	Machiavellianism and Dynamic Capability	- 0.26	-0.20	0.66	4.94	0.000	Negative and Significant	Not Supported
3	X → Y (H0 ₃)	Machiavellianism and Competitiveness	- 0.14	-0.13	0.02	4.47	0.000	Negative and Significant	Not Supported

Source: Amos 26.0 output on research data, 2020

References

- Adner, R., & Helfat, C. E. (2003). Corporate effects and dynamic managerial capabilities. *Strategic management journal*, 24(10), 1011-1025.
- Allport, G. W. (1937). Personality: A psychological interpretation.
- Astrachan, J. H., & Kolenko, T. A. (1994). A neglected factor explaining family business success: Human resource practices. *Family Business Review*, 7(3), 251-262.
- Astrachan, J. H., & Shanker, M. C. (2003). Family businesses' contribution to the US economy: A closer look. *Family Business Review*, 16(3), 211-219.
- Bamford, C. E., Bruton, G. D., & Hinson, Y. L. (2006). Founder/chief executive officer exit: a social capital perspective of new ventures. *Journal of small business management*, 44(2), 207-220.
- Bates, T. (1985). Entrepreneur human capital endowments and minority business viability. *Journal of Human Resources*, 540-554.
- Bednarz, J., Bieliński, T., Nikodemska-Wołowik, A., & Otukoya, A. (2017). Sources of the competitive advantage of family enterprises: an international approach focusing on China, Nigeria and Poland. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 5(2), 123.
- Bereczkei, T., Birkas, B., & Kerekes, Z. (2010). The presence of others, prosocial traits, machiavellianism. *Social Psychology*.
- Bird, B., & Brush, C. (2002). A gendered perspective on organizational creation. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 26(3), 41-65.
- Birley, S. (1986). Succession in the family firm: The inheritor's view. *Journal of small business management*, 24, 36.
- Breton-Miller, I. L., Miller, D., & Steier, L. P. (2004). Toward an integrative model of effective FOB succession. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 28(4), 305-328.
- Burt, R. S. (1997). The contingent value of social capital. *Administrative science quarterly*, 339-365.
- Cai, P. (2015). China's new economic crisis: Keeping the family business. *The Asialink Essays*, 7(1), 3-4.

- Carpenter, M. A., Geletkanycz, M. A., & Sanders, W. G. (2004). Upper echelons research revisited: Antecedents, elements, and consequences of top management team composition. *Journal of Management*, 30(6), 749-778.
- Chang, H.-J., Hou, J.-J., & Lin, S.-J. (2013). A MULTI-CASES COMPARATIVE APPROACH ON FORMING ELEMENTS OF DYNAMIC CAPABILITY. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 5(4).
- Christie, R., & Geis, F. L. (2013). *Studies in machiavellianism*: Academic Press.
- Danes, S. M., Lee, J., Stafford, K., & Heck, R. K. Z. (2008). The effects of ethnicity, families and culture on entrepreneurial experience: An extension of sustainable family business theory. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 13(03), 229-268.
- Danes, S. M., Rueter, M. A., Kwon, H. K., & Doherty, W. (2002). Family FIRO model: An application to family business. *Family Business Review*, 15(1), 31-43.
- Danes, S. M., Stafford, K., Haynes, G., & Amarapurkar, S. S. (2009). Family capital of family firms: Bridging human, social, and financial capital. *Family Business Review*, 22(3), 199-215.
- Danes, S. M., Stafford, K., & Loy, J. T.-C. (2007). Family business performance: The effects of gender and management. *Journal of Business Research*, 60(10), 1058-1069.
- Denison, D. R. (1990). *Corporate culture and organizational effectiveness*: John Wiley & Sons.
- Díez-Martín, F., Prado-Roman, C., & Blanco-González, A. (2013). Beyond legitimacy: legitimacy types and organizational success. *Management decision*.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., & Martin, J. A. (2000). Dynamic capabilities: what are they? *Strategic management journal*, 21(10-11), 1105-1121.
- Gargiulo, M., & Benassi, M. (2000). Trapped in your own net? Network cohesion, structural holes, and the adaptation of social capital. *Organization science*, 11(2), 183-196.
- Gaumer, C. J., & Shaffer, K. J. (2018). Family business succession: impact on supplier relations and customer management. *Human Resource Management International Digest*, 26(6), 1-4.
- Gibb Dyer Jr, W. (2006). Examining the "family effect" on firm performance. *Family Business Review*, 19(4), 253-273.
- Hambrick, D. C. (2007). Upper echelons theory: An update. In: Academy of Management Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510.
- Hambrick, D. C., Finkelstein, S., & Mooney, A. C. (2005). Executives sometimes lose it, just like the rest of us. *Academy of management review*, 30(3), 503-508.
- Harrison, J. S., Thurgood, G. R., Boivie, S., & Pfarrer, M. D. (2019). How a CEO's Personality Affects Their Company's Stock Price. *Harvard Business Review*, 4.
- Havvley, P. H. (2006). Evolution and Personality: A New Look at Machiavellianism.
- Haynes, G. W., Danes, S. M., & Stafford, K. (2011). Influence of federal disaster assistance on family business survival and success. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 19(2), 86-98.
- Hiller, N. J., & Hambrick, D. C. (2005). Conceptualizing executive hubris: the role of (hyper-) core self-evaluations in strategic decision-making. *Strategic management journal*, 26(4), 297-319.
- Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., Camp, S., & Sexton, D. (2002). *Strategic entrepreneurship*: Blackwell Oxford, UK.
- Hodson, G., Hogg, S. M., & MacInnis, C. C. (2009). The role of "dark personalities"(narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychopathy), Big Five personality factors, and ideology in explaining prejudice. *Journal of research in personality*, 43(4), 686-690.
- Ibrahim, Dumas, C., & McGuire, J. (2001). Strategic decision making in small family firms: an empirical investigation. *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, 12(1), 80-90.
- Ibrahim, & Ellis. (1994). Family business management: Concepts and practice, Dubuque, IA: Kendall. In: Hunt Publishing Company.
- Ibrahim, Soufani, K., & Lam, J. (2003). Family business training: a Canadian perspective. *Education+ Training*, 45(8/9), 474-482.
- Jones, D. N., & Paulhus, D. L. (2009). Machiavellianism.
- Kerig, P. K., & Stellwagen, K. K. (2010). Roles of callous-unemotional traits, narcissism, and Machiavellianism in childhood aggression. *Journal of Psychopathology and Behavioral Assessment*, 32(3), 343-352.
- Kisiel-Łowczyc, A. B. (2009). *Cultural Factors of Competitiveness in the Baltic Sea Region (BSR)*. Paper presented at the Economic Styles in the Process of EU Eastern Enlargement.

- Kwok-bun, C. (2013). Intimacy and its denial: When sons and daughters talk about fatherhood, marriage and work. In *International Handbook of Chinese Families* (pp. 307-312): Springer.
- Lank, A. G., & Lank, E. A. (1995). Legitimizing the gut feel: the role of intuition in business. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*.
- Lansberg, I. (1999). *Succeeding generations: Realizing the dream of families in business*: Harvard Business Review Press.
- Lee. (1999). Organizational learning in China. *Business Horizons*, 42(1), 37-44.
- Lee, Vargo, J., & Seville, E. (2013). Developing a tool to measure and compare organizations' resilience. *Natural hazards review*, 14(1), 29-41.
- Lubiński, M., Michalski, T., & Misala, J. (1995). Międzynarodowa konkurencyjność gospodarki. *Pojęcie i sposób mierzenia. Instytut Rozwoju i Studiów Strategicznych, Warszawa*, 47-48.
- Maltby, J., Day, L., & Macaskill, A. (2010). *Personality, individual differences and intelligence*: Pearson Education.
- Matyja, M. (2016). Resources based factors of competitiveness of agricultural enterprises. *Management*, 20(1), 368-381.
- McIlwain, D. (2003). Bypassing empathy: A Machiavellian theory of mind and sneaky power.
- Miller, Steier, L., & Le Breton-Miller, I. (2003). Lost in time: Intergenerational succession, change, and failure in family business. *Journal of business venturing*, 18(4), 513-531.
- Mokhber, M., Gi Gi, T., Abdul Rasid, S. Z., Vakilbashi, A., Mohd Zamil, N., & Woon Seng, Y. (2017). Succession planning and family business performance in SMEs. *Journal of management development*, 36(3), 330-347.
- Moore, C. W. (2008). *Managing small business: An entrepreneurial emphasis*: Cengage Learning EMEA.
- Mroziewski, M. (2011). Konkurencyjność podmiotów we współczesnej gospodarce rynkowej. *Rocznik Naukowy Wydziału Zarządzania w Ciechanowie*, 5(1-4), 117-128.
- Niehm, L. S., Swinney, J., & Miller, N. J. (2008). Community social responsibility and its consequences for family business performance. *Journal of small business management*, 46(3), 331-350.
- Nolan, T., Desmond, K., Herlich, R., & Hardy, S. (1986). Knowledge of cystic fibrosis in patients and their parents. *Pediatrics*, 77(2), 229-235.
- Onuoha, B. C. (2012). Professionalizing family businesses in the south-east region of Nigeria. *International Business and Management*, 5(1), 153-161.
- Oughton, E., & Wheelock, J. (2003). A capabilities approach to sustainable household livelihoods¹With thanks to the Economic and Social Research Council for funding 'Enterprising livelihoods in rural households: new and old ways of working' Award number R000238213 on which the empirical work is based. *Review of Social Economy*, 61(1), 1-22.
- Perret, S. T., Burnett, M. F., & Richardson, W. B. (2017). Perceptions of the Importance of Succession Planning in Family Owned Businesses. *Academy of Business Research Journal*, 3, 44-63.
- Pilch, I. (2008). Machiavellianism, emotional intelligence and social competence: Are Machiavellians interpersonally skilled? *Polish Psychological Bulletin*, 39(3), 158-164.
- Poza, E. J. (2013). *Family business*: Cengage Learning.
- Rauthmann, J. F., & Will, T. (2011). Proposing a multidimensional Machiavellianism conceptualization. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*, 39(3), 391-403.
- Reeves, M., & Deimler, M. (2012). Adaptability: The new competitive advantage. *Own the Future: 50 Ways to Win from the Boston Consulting Group*, 19-26.
- Ribot, T. (1896). Pathological Pleasures and Pains. *The Monist*, 6(2), 176-187.
- Robbins, S. P., Judge, T. A., & Sanghi, S. (2007). *Organizational Behavior [with CD]*: Prentice-Hall of India.
- Sakalaki, M., Richardson, C., & Thépaut, Y. (2007). Machiavellianism and economic opportunism. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 37(6), 1181-1190.
- Salvato, C., & Melin, L. (2008). Creating value across generations in family-controlled businesses: The role of family social capital. *Family Business Review*, 21(3), 259-276.
- Schein, E. H. (2010). *Organizational culture and leadership* (Vol. 2): John Wiley & Sons.
- Sifneos, P. E. (1973). The prevalence of 'alexithymic' characteristics in psychosomatic patients. *Psychotherapy and psychosomatics*, 22(2-6), 255-262.
- Simsek, Z., Heavey, C., & Veiga, J. F. (2010). The impact of CEO core self-evaluation on the firm's entrepreneurial orientation. *Strategic management journal*, 31(1), 110-119.

- Stafford, K., Bhargava, V., Danes, S. M., Haynes, G., & Brewton, K. E. (2010). Factors associated with long-term survival of family businesses: Duration analysis. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 31(4), 442-457.
- Stafford, K., Duncan, K. A., Dane, S., & Winter, M. (1999). A research model of sustainable family businesses. *Family Business Review*, 12(3), 197-208.
- Subramaniam, M., & Youndt, M. A. (2005). The influence of intellectual capital on the types of innovative capabilities. *Academy of Management journal*, 48(3), 450-463.
- Sutton, J., & Keogh, E. (2000). Social competition in school: Relationships with bullying, Machiavellianism and personality. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 70(3), 443-456.
- Tantrabundit, P., & Narkbunnum, W. (2018). *The Effects of CEO's Personality on Knowledge Transfer and Innovative Performance in Thai SMEs*. Paper presented at the 2018 3rd Technology Innovation Management and Engineering Science International Conference (TIMES-iCON).
- Utami, C. W., Bernardus, D., & Shinta, G. (2015). The Pattern Analysis of Family Business Succession A Study on Medium Scale Family Business in Indonesia.
- Veselka, L., Schermer, J. A., Martin, R. A., & Vernon, P. A. (2010). Relations between humor styles and the Dark Triad traits of personality. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 48(6), 772-774.
- Volmer, J., Koch, I. K., & Göritz, A. S. (2016). The bright and dark sides of leaders' dark triad traits: Effects on subordinates' career success and well-being. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 101, 413-418.
- Wang, & Chen, X. (2019). Recognizing CEO personality and its impact on business performance: Mining linguistic cues from social media. *Information & Management*, 103173.
- Winne, J. F., & Gittinger, J. W. (1973). An introduction to the personality assessment system. *Journal of Community Psychology*, 1(2), 99-163.
- Wong, C. W. (2013). Leveraging environmental information integration to enable environmental management capability and performance. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 49(2), 114-136.
- Woodley, H. J., & Allen, N. J. (2014). The dark side of equity sensitivity. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 67, 103-108.
- Zahra, S. A., Sapienza, H. J., & Davidsson, P. (2006). Entrepreneurship and dynamic capabilities: A review, model and research agenda. *Journal of Management studies*, 43(4), 917-955.
- Zali, R., & Sheydayaee, J. (2013). Determinants of Corporate Social Responsibility, Dynamic Capability and Financial Performance (Cases Study: Accepted Firms in Tehran Stock Exchange Market). *International Journal of Financial Management*, 3(2).
- Zopiatis, A., & Constanti, P. (2012). Extraversion, openness and conscientiousness: The route to transformational leadership in the hotel industry. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 33(1), 86-104.

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